

Grammatical features of Pakistani English: A Corpus Analysis of Pakistani English Newspapers and Magazines

Research Article

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Publication Details

Received: July 22, 2023

Accepted: August 25, 2023

Published: September 30, 2023

Abstract

The paper presents a corpus analysis conducted on the written corpus of Pakistani English. The corpus, created by the authors, is derived from the most widely circulated English newspapers and magazines in Pakistan. The analysis employs Sketch Engine and utilizes two models, namely Galloway and Rose (2015) and Jenkins (2009), to identify the distinctive grammatical features of Pakistani English in the corpus. The selection criteria for examining grammatical features are also grounded in these two models. The study focuses on the analysis of specific grammatical aspects, including (i) the use of adverbs, (ii) the use of the definite article, (iii) plurality, (iv) the use of yes/no questions, and (v) reduplication. The findings reveal that Pakistani English exhibits variations in the placement of adverbs and the usage of the definite article 'the'. Plurality is a prevalent feature, with writers often treating uncountable nouns as countable in their compositions. However, the data does

not indicate any deviations regarding two features: yes/no questions and reduplication. Despite being a less recognized variety of English, primarily due to the limited documentation of its features, this paper contributes to the establishment of Pakistani English as a recognized linguistic variety.

Keywords: Grammar, Pakistani English, Corpus Analysis, Written Corpus, Language Variety

1. Introduction

English holds institutional status in outer circle countries (Ahn, 2017), and the term “New Englishes” is designated for such linguistic varieties (Gunesequera, 1989), popularized by Pride (1982). In these contexts, English symbolizes elitism and signifies upward social and cultural mobility (Monfared & Khatib, 2018). Responding to Selinker's (1972) characterization of fossilization and errors in emerging varieties, Kachru (1985) introduced the concept of “indigenization” to describe the localization of these varieties in outer circle countries. This indigenization primarily occurs under the influence of the first language (Bhela, 1999; Sinha et al., 2009; Derakhshan & Karimi, 2015; Buriro et al., 2015). Such varieties might be labeled as deviant due to a lack of documentation (Quirk, 1985), hindering their recognition (Hamid & Baldauf, 2013). Viewing idiosyncratic features of New Englishes as a consequence of inadequate command over native varieties further obstructs their acknowledgment (Anchimbe, 2007). Schneider's (2007) model terms this process the “nativization phase,” wherein a native variety assimilates into outer circle culture and acquires independent features. Pakistani English (PE) undergoes a similar process, but the insufficient documentation of its features poses a challenge for ELT practitioners: whether to treat such features as errors or not (Hamid, Zhu & Baldauf, 2014). This research aims to document some grammatical features of PE.

In the context of Braj Kachru's work legitimizing various English varieties worldwide, establishing Pakistani English as a distinct dialect becomes imperative, given its unique features. A dialect achieves recognition when it possesses distinctive pronunciation, vocabulary, and grammar (Yule, 2022). Grammar, in particular, is a crucial aspect to study for establishing Pakistani English as a distinct dialect of English. Mahboob (2013) notes a lack of research in this area, indicating that earlier studies merely acknowledged the unique features of Pakistani English without providing detailed explanations. Presently, the situation persists, echoing Mahboob's observations (ibid).

1.1 Research Gap

In the context of the growing field of corpus linguistics associated with the World Englishes (WE) paradigm, there is a limited body of research dedicated to comprehending the features of PE, particularly within the framework of established models (Mahboob, 2014). Language encompasses various facets that necessitate objective examination. The grammatical characteristics of PE remain insufficiently explored, particularly in the context of corpus-based studies (Mahmood, 2009).

1.2 Research Objective

To investigate the grammatical features of Pakistani English, this study examines the corpus derived from Pakistani newspapers and magazines, utilizing insights from two South Asian English models.

1.3 Research Question

What grammatical features characterize Pakistani English in the corpus of Pakistani newspapers and magazines?

1.4 Analysis of Grammar

Grammar analysis has been a significant focus since the latter part of the twentieth century. Early analyses centered on collecting texts, typically through convenient sampling, and were manually examined. With technological advancements, contemporary analyses involve the use of software to analyze larger corpora, introducing a more systematic approach to grammar analysis (Biber, 2006). The corpus analysis method has been applied to various grammatical features across languages, such as examining differences between old and new word functions in Arabic (Almujaiwel, 2017), exploring passive voice usage (Granger, 1983), and investigating nominal structures (de Hann, 1989).

In the context of PE, several works have delved into its grammar, particularly in terms of differentiation from standard varieties like British English (BrE) or American English (AmE) (Mahboob, 2004). While previous studies have addressed PE's grammar, corpus-based grammatical analyses of PE have recently gained traction. For instance, Azher, Mahmood and Shah (2018) explored register in Pakistani academic writings, and Alvi, Mahmood and Rasool (2016) investigated the sub-register of PE in newspaper editorials. This current research study also employs a corpus-based approach for grammar analysis in the context of PE.

1.4 Corpus-Based Analysis of Grammar

In recent decades, the analysis of grammar in linguistic studies has become a prominent approach. Collecting and scrutinizing extensive language data reveals systematic variations in the structure and function of language variants (Biber, 2006). Despite the rise of communicative approaches, the significance of grammar analysis remains crucial, especially with the aid of computer-assisted language learning techniques and available electronic tools for language analysis (Borin & Dahlöf, 1999).

Towards the end of the 20th century, research on grammar saw a simultaneous upward trend, linked with the use of electronically assisted software programs for analysis. Initially, corpus-based, computer-assisted grammatical analysis focused primarily on concordance. However, by the turn of the century, a corpus-based approach to grammar emerged, allowing for a shift from linear descriptions to multi-faceted and dynamic analyses, incorporating a register-based approach (Conrad, 2000). The combination of these approaches has heightened the importance of statistically profiling a language, contributing to developments on theoretical and computational fronts (Roland, Dick & Elman, 2007). However, relying solely on concordances or frequencies is insufficient to fully comprehend the extent and nature of language variation and use. Insightful input and observations from researchers are necessary to enhance quantitative results. This mixed-method approach is employed in the current study, emphasizing the importance of a theoretical foundation for the pedagogical implementation of corpus-based grammatical analysis results (Wu, 2008).

The effective amalgamation of theoretical and computational components has made corpus-based grammar analysis a common phenomenon. For example, Klavan (2014) studied the grammatical

synonymy of the Estonian language, revealing patterns aligned with previous research and theoretical foundations after a thorough analysis of the written corpus through regression models.

Corpus-based grammar analysis holds promising implications for language documentation. Dictionaries, crucial resources in language documentation, can be enriched through corpus-based studies. James (2010) conducted a study in the context of the English dictionary, focusing on the dual use of prepositional 'at' and infinitive 'at' with the verb 'aim,' emphasizing the importance of corpus-based methods for determining usage patterns and principles.

Corpus analysis is a valuable tool for English Language Teaching (ELT) classroom activities, providing teachers with empirical foundations and potential solutions by utilizing large language texts. Sometimes, these solutions address peculiar language behaviors and usage patterns not found in dictionaries and grammar books (Recski, 2006).

Among the three major areas identified by Biber, Conrad and Reppen (1994), grammar stands out as a strong area of research for corpus-based studies. It offers empirical foundations and facilitates comparative and contrastive analyses across registers and varieties. Corpus-based approaches to grammar extend beyond grammarians and linguists, shedding light on people's worldviews based on language use. The dynamic applied nature of corpus-based grammar analysis is evident (Coffin, Hewings & O'Halloran, 2014).

In Pakistani English, recent corpus-based studies have explored grammatical features. For instance, the emergence of ditransitive verb forms not present in BrE, along with increased localization and nativization in certain genres, has been noted (Aziz & Mahmood, 2012). Other studies highlighted distinct patterns of linking adverbials and the avoidance of cognate objects, setting Pakistani English apart as a unique variety (Jameel et al., 2014; Ahmed, 2014). Conjunctions, particularly the overuse of 'and' for clarity and connection, have also been studied in Pakistani Written English (Khan & Choudhary, 2017). This study builds on these efforts.

1.5 Research Design

This research employs corpus analysis methodology as the primary approach to investigate the features of Pakistani English in a corpus constructed from English newspapers and magazines in Pakistan. According to Kennedy (1998), the compilation of extensive electronic texts and their analysis on various linguistic levels has emerged as a distinct methodology in recent decades. Biber (1990) acknowledges the methodology's emergence, addressing intuitive criticisms by emphasizing its potential to comprehend the nature of a language due to the substantial corpus size. Over time, the corpus methodology has evolved and become sophisticated, incorporating numerous improvements from various researchers (Arppe et al., 2010). Numerous studies, including those by Pearson (2007), Rogers (2003), Rodriguez (2005), Diniz (2007), Lombard (1997), and others, have applied this methodology, yielding valuable results.

An intriguing aspect of this methodology is its definition and explanation, which primarily revolves around procedural and practical terms rather than theoretical underpinnings. It is essential to clarify that despite adopting the corpus linguistics methodology, this study, like others, employs a mixed-method approach at the analysis level. The results are initially presented quantitatively and subsequently discussed qualitatively.

2. Data Collection

2.1 Corpus Construction

The corpus comprises the written content extracted from three English newspapers and two English magazines published and circulated in Pakistan. These newspapers and magazines represent the register commonly used in journalistic writing, offering a comprehensive coverage of the diverse functions and features of English language usage in Pakistan.

Recognizing the significance of corpora in language studies, particularly within the context of modern research in corpus linguistics, this study underscores the distinct methodology that corpora provide. In Pakistan, efforts to compile corpora are in their nascent stages, with various researchers attempting to construct their own corpora. However, the accessibility of such corpora is often limited, and those available may not align with the specific requirements of this study. Consequently, the researchers compiled their own corpus, focusing exclusively on the written register and incorporating newspaper and magazine articles covering a variety of themes. Table 1 provides a summary of the sources, the number of articles, and their respective word count/size.

Table 2.1 Number of words

Source	Articles	No. of Words
Dawn	73	68261
Express	63	47939
The Nation	61	57766
Herald	24	51940
Newsline	20	23984
Total	241	249890

Graph 2.1 Number of Words

Graph 2.2 Number of Articles

2.2 Sources of the Corpus

All corpus sources, including newspapers and magazines, were accessed through their online websites. Their electronic versions were copied and pasted into text files for further analysis. Although these publications are primarily circulated in Pakistan, their online availability allows them to be accessed globally. The Dawn, Express Tribune, and The Nation are prominent national English dailies in Pakistan with extensive circulation. Herald and Newslines are widely-read English magazines.

The selection of these specific newspapers and magazines was guided by several considerations. Firstly, they rank among the most circulated and widely accepted platforms in print media. Secondly, their digital presence makes them conducive for corpus collection and subsequent analysis. Thirdly, these publications showcase the writings of some of the most literate English writers in Pakistan, lending credibility and accuracy to the corpus.

Furthermore, at the time of data collection, no corpora for Pakistani English were available. Consequently, the researchers undertook the development of their own corpora specifically for this research study.

2.3 Initial Processing of the Corpus

The articles for the corpus were randomly extracted from newspapers and magazines issued or published in January 2018. These articles were saved in a text-only format, and each file was named and coded, such as <Jan08Dawn2018(1)>.

Once all the individual files were compiled, the entire corpus was consolidated into one large <.txt> file. This consolidation was facilitated by the corpus analysis software, which easily supports this file format. A summary of the corpus is presented in Table 2.

3. Data Analysis

The present study employed the methodology of corpus linguistics to analyze the corpus of Pakistani English. This methodology has evolved as a distinctive approach, deviating from traditional modes of inquiry. While its primary data quantification might suggest a purely quantitative nature, the methodology is inherently a mixed method, given the interpretative nature of its results and their dependence on qualitative discussions. However, it is not commonly labeled as a mixed method approach.

The application of this methodology necessitates the use of software for corpus analysis. In this study, the software utilized is 'Sketch Engine,' designed for lexicographers to assess and analyze the behavior and grammatical features of words in large corpora (Bonial, Hargraves & Palmer, 2013).

3.1 Summary of Collected Data for Corpus

Table 3.1 Summary of data

Type of Data Source	Newspapers	[Daily]	[Dawn, The Express Tribune, The Nation]
	Magazines	[Monthly]	[Herald, Newslines]
No. of News Collected	Newspapers	Dawn	73
		The Express Tribune	63
		The Nation	61
	Magazines	Herald	24
		Newslines	21
Timeframe	Newspapers	Dawn	January 01, 2018 – January 31, 2018
		The Express Tribune	
		The Nation	
	Magazines	Herald	January 2018 Issues
		Newslines	
Codes	Newspapers	Dawn	01JanD
		The Express Tribune	01JanE
		The Nation	01JanT
	Magazines	Herald	1HEJan/2HEJan
		Newslines	1NLJan/2NLJan

Graph Error! No text of specified style in document..1 Words Theme-wise

3.2 Kinds of Analyses

The following elements were examined in the corpus. These grammatical features are drawn from the South Asian Englishes model proposed by Galloway and Rose (2015).

Table 3.2 Grammatical Features

Grammatical Features
Plurality
Yes/No Questions
Adverbs
Use of the article ‘the’
Reduplication

3.2.1 Analysis Type I: Word Lists

The Wordlist feature in Sketch Engine produces a comprehensive list of all words in the corpus along with their respective frequencies. This feature proves valuable for identifying the most frequently used words in the corpus. In the current study, the Wordlist feature was specifically employed to analyze plural forms.

3.2.1.1 Plurality

Through the word lists, it becomes easier through a manual sifting, to recognize those nouns which are otherwise uncountable but have been treated as countable and made the plural of in the given text.

3.2.2 Analysis Type 2: Parts of Speech

Not all corpus analysis software programs come equipped with this feature by default. Typically, they do not assist researchers in easily sorting various parts of speech, making it challenging to estimate the frequency and nature of word classes in the text. This consideration played a role in selecting Sketch Engine as the software for analyzing parts of speech in this research study's corpus. The POS search feature in the software was utilized to extract various types of adverbs for further analysis.

3.2.2.1 Adverbs

Upon uploading the corpus and accessing the dashboard, a command to extract adverbs was issued in the software, resulting in the generation of a list of adverbs in Microsoft Excel format. The researchers identified five types of adverbs: manner, time, place, degree, and frequency. However, the analysis did not conclude there; another analysis technique was employed for a more in-depth examination of adverbs, as discussed in the following section.

3.2.3 Analysis Type 3: Concordance

This form of analysis is employed to understand the context surrounding a word or keyword, known as Keyword in Context (KWIC). Concordance analysis enabled the researchers to compile a list of all instances where the keyword was used, along with its contextual information, for further analysis. The following features were examined using this analytical technique:

3.2.3.1 Adverbs

Following the initial analysis in the Parts of Speech analysis type, the extracted and selected adverbs were sought in the corpus. A concordance list was generated for each adverb, enabling researchers to identify instances where the adverbs were used in a manner deviating from native varieties.

3.2.3.2 Yes/No Questions

The keywords 'yes' and 'no' were separately entered into the search bar in two distinct instances, and the concordance contexts were extracted. The generated lists aided in identifying the contexts in which 'yes' and 'no' might have been used differently than in inner circle Englishes.

3.2.3.4 Article 'the'

The keyword 'the' was searched to analyze its deviant uses from native English varieties.

3.2.4 Analysis Type 4: N-Grams

To understand the use of words in pairs, Sketch Engine offers a feature that, after uploading the entire corpus, sifts through all the words used in pairs. This facilitates researchers in discerning the relationships between paired words, allowing for a convenient examination of words in pairs of two.

3.2.4.1 Reduplication

For the current study, bi-grams were extracted to identify instances of reduplication.

4. Findings

4.1 Adverbs

Table 4.1 Consolidated data of the number of actual and deviated adverbs

No	Item	Total frequency	Deviated frequency
1	Overall adverbs in the corpus	11398	---
2	Selected adverbs	1764	236
3	Adverbs of manner	Effectively	5
		Quickly	5
		Actually	1
		Clearly	15
		Politically	5
		Now	150
4	Adverbs of time	Recently	4
		Currently	4
		Previously	2
		Subsequently	1
5	Adverbs of place	There	9
		Here	24
6	Adverbs of frequency	Always	4
		Never	2
7	Adverbs of degree	Really	2
		Quite	3

Graph 4.1 Adverbs

Tables 5 to 9 showcase examples of deviated and shuffled adverbs of all five types in context:

4.2 Adverbs of Manner

Table 4.2 Adverbs of manner: Placed in middle and beginning rather than ending

-
- 1 Solutions will depend on *effectively* implementing Vision 2025
 - 2 It will have to persuade Saudi Arabia and the UAE to *effectively* move against these fund raisers in their respective countries
 - 3 To *effectively* deal with the menace of armed militancy in the country, Khosa proposes a....
 - 4 we were back in the good books of the US and *quickly* became its non-Nato ally.
 - 5 *Actually* it is morally wrong to send Afghan refugees back to Afghanistan.
 - 6 Many of these beneficiaries should be *clearly* ineligible for public representation. (Adverb needs to be between the two aux)
 - 7 The 40-second video that went viral *clearly* shows that conduct of some of the reporters present at the Foreign Office
 - 8 The civilian leadership *clearly* thinks that it has to break the shackles
 - 9 *Politically* there has been much confusion but in terms of the economy
 - 10 Christians in Balochistan are *politically* represented, on seats reserved for minorities
-

Adverbs of manner in native varieties of English are typically positioned at the beginning or end of a sentence. However, this study's data revealed that Pakistani writers often place them in the middle. This deviation might stem from the influence of local languages spoken in the region. The researchers speculate that natural intuition, coupled with the impact of the writers' first language(s), may be at play here. To emphasize the meaning of a sentence, writers may feel that placing such adverbs in the

middle position, particularly around verbs, is more suitable for effectively communicating the message to the audience.

4.3 Adverbs of Time

Here are some additional examples of unconventional changes in the position of adverbs of time:

Table 4.3 Adverbs of time deviated in position placed in middle rather than beginning or ending

1	Bacha Khan University in Charsadda <i>recently</i> banned mixed gatherings on its campus.
2	As a result, epidemics such as chikungunya have <i>recently</i> spread across the metropolis.
3	knowledge of the committee the Establishment Division <i>recently</i> changed the weightage of different parameters
4	Its mayor <i>recently</i> visited Pakistan to market London as a globally desirable choice
5	The government is <i>currently</i> considering another approach to the debt markets before March
6	Three types of political parties <i>currently</i> populate the political stage in the restive province
7	there are <i>currently</i> 2,445,357 women living in Fata
8	He was <i>previously</i> The Daily Telegraph correspondent in Pakistan.
9	The EU s chief negotiator, Michel Barnier, has <i>previously</i> gone on record
10	She <i>subsequently</i> called for a commercial break.
11	He was <i>subsequently</i> arrested and charged with double murder and hate crimes.

Similar to adverbs of manner, adverbs of time are typically placed at the beginning or end. However, Pakistani English writers use them in a deviant manner. The researchers posit that the reasons for this deviation might align with those of adverbs of manner, such as the influence of the mother tongue, the writer's and readers' intuition, or a combination of the two. Notably, during the research process, when the results were shared with colleagues and individuals from the ELT field, they struggled to distinguish between the norms of native varieties and the deviated forms. Furthermore, these deviations feel so normal to Pakistani users that they often perceive no issue with positioning these adverbs in the middle.

4.4 Adverbs of Place

Table 4.4 Adverbs of place put in middle rather than beginning or ending

1	The Portias are <i>there</i> to protect the poor and ignorant
2	however, the question <i>here</i> is: when will the apex courts Excalibur be back in its sheath?
3	Most parents <i>here</i> haven t explored the potential of sports.
4	The purpose <i>here</i> is not to undermine the achievements of K-P police in the last four years
5	However, the lesson <i>here</i> is not to dismiss the need to protect our religious minorities
6	Doctors <i>here</i> think the child will not survive without treatment in Hyderabad

Adverbs of place are typically positioned at the end. However, influenced by norms in local languages and the desire to enhance communication clarity, writers in local genres often feel the need to place them in the middle. This deviation, like others, is normalized in society. Even the researchers

themselves faced challenges in identifying them as deviations until referring to the established rules of native variety norms.

4.5 Adverbs of Frequency

Table 4.5 Adverbs of frequency put in beginning rather than middle or ending

1	<i>Always</i> , it is night-time, when suddenly terrorists hiding and waiting for the police
2	<i>Always</i> mobilising an impressive amount of documentary evidence, she explored ...
3	<i>Never</i> really asked in the sense that while the Haqqanis have been a point of diff

In the grammatical rules of native varieties of English, it is prescribed that adverbs of frequency, such as "always" and "never," strictly cannot be used at the beginning of a sentence. However, Pakistani writers in magazines and newspapers occasionally overlook this rule and use them according to their own discretion, with editors and readers also appearing complacent.

4.6 Adverbs of Degree

Table 4.6 Adverbs of degree placed in beginning or ending rather than middle

1	Not too bad <i>really</i> .
2	<i>Quite</i> correctly, it has been pointed out that liberals are over-credited in Pakistan
3	<i>Quite</i> a remarkable achievement after trillions spent, close to 2,400 US soldiers
4	<i>Quite</i> apart from the ideological and political reasons for telling the stories that I

When analyzing the grammatical rules of native varieties of English, it became apparent that adverbs of degree, such as "quite" and "really," should not be used at the beginning or end of a sentence. However, it was observed that indigenous writers in Pakistan tended to use such adverbs in a deviant manner. The findings outlined here underscore the varied use of adverb positions in the syntax of Pakistani English, with the most variation observed in adverbs of time, place, and frequency.

Multiple reasons may contribute to this phenomenon, as envisioned by the researchers of this study. Firstly, not every writer has undergone formal education in English grammar, which, in almost all cases, follows native English grammar. Even if writers have received schooling that includes English grammar classes, many do not seem to possess a rigorous and robust knowledge of English grammar rules. Moreover, writers often use English for communicative and functional purposes, prioritizing effective communication over strict adherence to grammatical rules.

Secondly, the inter-language effect may be a reason for the deviation from native English norms in Pakistani English. Adverbs, serving to enhance the function of the verb, may be influenced by cultural norms and semantically loaded aspects, prompting writers to deviate from standard norms. Writers in Pakistani English may feel the same freedom in using adverbs as they do in local languages, where adverbs are used more indiscriminately. Additionally, emphasizing the adverb or its meaning may lead a writer to deviate from norms, as placing the adverb in a different position can help convey the intended semantic value of an utterance more effectively to readers who may be less aware of native English rules.

The third reason could be the multicultural and multilingual setting of Pakistan. Urdu, while a major lingua franca within the country, is the mother tongue of only a fraction of the population. Other languages like Punjabi, Sindhi, Balochi, Pashto, Seraiki, etc., each come with distinct rules, norms, and conventions. The coexistence of more than seventy languages in Pakistan leads to frequent overlapping of linguistic features and an amalgamated influence of languages. In such a cultural milieu, it wouldn't be surprising for English to exhibit changes, including in the use of adverbs. The corpus used in this study comprises articles written by writers of diverse ethnicities and mother tongues, born and brought up in varying atmospheres, explaining the varying use of adverbs on cultural and social levels.

Fourth, in recent years, there has been a significant influx of literature and written text from around the world. Writers of English from various nationalities often experiment with language, incorporating elements of their mother tongue or local languages. The frequent interaction between writers, authors, journalists, and media persons through the internet and global connectivity events has led to an accommodation of language differences, making the rules of only one standard somewhat irrelevant for many.

4.7 Use of Article 'the'

The use of the article 'the' in Pakistani English is one of the most frequently deviated features among South Asian Englishes. In the corpus of the current study, two trends were observed during the data analysis: either the article in question was used in places where it was not necessary, or it was entirely omitted in places where its use was essential. Out of many instances, the following are a few examples of deviated insertion or omission of the definite article 'the'. The italic letters signify unnecessary inclusion, and the italicized nouns or adjectives signify the absence of 'the' before them.

Table 4.7 Article 'the'

- | | |
|---|--|
| 1 | I also appeal to the President of <i>USA</i> to inform us as to why the only drone in Khyber Agency was... (omission) |
| 2 | We had requested earlier to <i>USA</i> authorities but your concerned authorities did not cooperate with the Pakistani government and Pakistani investigators. (omission) |
| 3 | Furthermore, he has Justice Baqar Najafi's damning report on the Punjab government in his hand and has all the arsenal to lock Lahore down as a New Year's present to <i>Pakistani politics</i> . (omission) |
| 4 | SOLUTIONS are context specific. Outside context, <i>the</i> solution becomes a problem (insertion) |
| 5 | <i>The</i> rule of the jungle. (insertion) |

A significant deviation in the use of the definite article was observed. Writers either used this article redundantly where it was not needed, omitted it where necessary, or inconsistently used it within the same context in different places within one write-up.

One of the primary reasons behind this feature in Pakistani English is the absence of the concept of articles in almost all local languages. None of the major local languages have any articles, let alone the definite article. Numerous global studies have emphasized the importance of this fact. It is not surprising that users of English in this country may struggle with this rule, even after a lifetime

immersed in an environment filled with English novels, Hollywood movies, online and web series, magazines, etc. If a writer continues to make this vital mistake, it should be acknowledged as a reflection of the writers' cognition and cultural influence from local languages rather than a simple error. For instance, ethnic Baloch users of Sindhi language often encounter confusion between masculine and feminine distinctions in Sindhi, a feature that does not exist in Balochi. This confusion is not an error but a characteristic of the Northern dialect of Sindhi.

Another challenge contributing to the problematic nature of this feature, given its common and frequent occurrence in a deviant manner, is the variation in resources used for teaching and learning. The researchers encountered numerous resources guiding learners on the usage of this article, each differing in the number of rules and the accuracy of their explanations. This fluidity of rules has the potential to confuse learners.

4.8 Plurality

The following words are typically considered uncountable and cannot be pluralized. However, the data indicates the following deviations:

Table 4.8 Plurality Data

	Word		Word
1	Elites	13	Commonalities
2	Provisions	14	Installations
3	incomes	15	Densities
4	Freedoms	16	Truths
5	waters	17	Creations
6	Populations	18	Liberties
7	Jurisdictions	19	cost-benefits
8	Fibers	20	farm-lands
9	Damages	21	Excesses
10	Profits	22	Goings
11	Myriads	23	Proximities
12	magnitudes	24	administrations

The tendency to pluralize uncountable nouns is prevalent among Pakistani English users and writers. They often form plurals of mass nouns in both spoken and written language. The instances presented here are limited due to the corpus's size, and they come from columnists who have been educated in systems where native varieties are considered the standard authority. Despite careful writing and subsequent editing, these pluralizations went unnoticed and were not treated as errors. It can be assumed that in spoken Pakistani English, there is an even higher tendency to treat mass nouns as countable.

One reason for this phenomenon is the difference in the conceptualization of nouns in local languages compared to English. There are instances where a noun that is countable in local languages becomes uncountable in English, and vice versa. For example, "land" in English is an uncountable noun, but in local languages, it may be treated as countable. Another example is "hair," which is a mass noun in native English varieties but treated as countable in local languages. The confusion

arises in the ambiguous areas of the countable-uncountable continuum, influenced significantly by the writers' first language when deviating from native English norms regarding plurality.

4.9 Yes/No Tag Questions

No instances of deviant yes/no tag questions were found in the selected corpus for this study. This absence may be attributed to the likelihood that such tag questions are predominantly a feature of spoken language rather than written discourse.

4.10 Reduplication

No instances of reduplication were identified in the selected corpus for this study. In this study, reduplication was operationally defined as the repetition of a word to emphasize its meaning or importance. Reduplication is a common linguistic feature in Pakistan, often experienced in informal spoken language. However, the absence of reduplication in the written corpus used for this study may be attributed to the formal nature of written language. Unlike in spoken language, where such occurrences may go unnoticed, written language, including writing software programs like MS Word, is more likely to flag reduplication as an error, prompting writers or editors to review their language use.

5. Discussion

5.1 Use of Adverbs

The deviations observed in the placement of adverbs in Pakistani English, focusing on the categories of adverbs of manner, time, place, degree, and frequency, were not overly frequent but substantial enough to corroborate findings by Galloway and Rose (2015) and Jenkins (2009). The researchers referred to an online dictionary from Cambridge University for the established rules regarding adverb placement:

- Adverbs of manner are typically placed at the end but occasionally in the middle position, especially if the object is not the focal point of the sentence or is lengthy.
- Adverbs of place usually find their place at the end of the sentence but may occasionally appear at the beginning.
- Adverbs of time generally occupy the end position but can be shifted to the front for emphasis.
- Adverbs of degree, such as 'really,' 'very,' and 'quite,' are usually placed in the middle, while expressions like 'a lot' or 'a bit' may be positioned at the front.
- Adverbs of frequency commonly occur in the middle but might also appear at the front or end. However, adverbs like 'always,' 'ever,' and 'never' are not typically placed at the front.

Contrary to conventional grammar rules, which suggest that adverbs of time predominantly occur at the end or, on occasion, at the beginning of a sentence, Pakistani English often employs adverbs of time in the middle of sentences.

Although instances of misplaced adverbs were not highly frequent, they were substantial enough to make a noticeable impact. The systematic exploration of the reasons behind such deviations in the context of Pakistani English remains under-researched. No prior research specifically addressing the placement of adverbs in Pakistani English was found by the researchers. Nevertheless, the complexity of adverb usage, with its various subtypes each having distinct rules for placement, could contribute to users deviating from established norms, whether knowingly or unknowingly.

A study by Ko (2016), analyzing adverb placement in the corpora of ten major English varieties globally, including Indian English, aligns with the observations of the current study. Ko found no consistent pattern in the placement of adverbs across the ten varieties, and in Indian English, a slight tendency to position adverbs before verbs was noted. Ko attributes the flexible placement of adverbs to the multilingual nature of societies worldwide, where English is often learned as a second language, leading to the influence of local languages on English usage. This insight resonates with the linguistic landscape of Pakistani society, characterized by multilingualism, suggesting that the interplay of languages may contribute to the flexible and deviated placement of adverbs in sentences.

5.2 Use of Article ‘the’

Galloway and Rose (2015) and Jenkins (2009) concur that users of South Asian Englishes frequently deviate from inner circle norms, particularly concerning the use of articles, especially the definite article. The analysis of the current corpus aligns with this observed tendency.

A notable phenomenon is the inconsistency in the use of the article 'the' with the same nouns. In one instance, 'the' is used with a noun, and in another, it is omitted with the same noun.

Miller (2005) emphatically states that the use of English articles poses challenges for non-native users, primarily due to the absence of an article system in their native languages. This holds true for the local languages in Pakistan, none of which incorporates an article system. Consequently, correct and judicious use of articles becomes problematic. The researchers, drawing on their extensive experience as ELT practitioners, share a similar observation. Despite detailed instruction, their students often struggle with the accurate use of definite articles, grappling with the proper placement. Crompton (2011) takes this further, asserting that even speakers of languages with article systems encounter difficulties in using the English article system, with the most common errors occurring in the use of the definite article. This study affirms Crompton's findings, as the research results indicate a notable tendency toward the overuse and deviant use of the definite article 'the' in Pakistani English.

Hasbún (2009) echoes similar findings, noting that learners in the context of Costa Rica tend to overuse articles due to interference from the mother tongue of EFL students. Similarly, in the context of the current study, a pronounced inclination toward overusing definite articles was observed. Consequently, it can be asserted once again that there is a substantial tendency toward the overuse and non-standard use of the definite article 'the' in Pakistani English.

5.3 Plurality

According to Galloway & Rose (2015), individuals in South Asian countries often treat uncountable nouns as countable and exhibit a tendency to pluralize uncountable nouns. The corpus analysis conducted in this study validates this observation for Pakistani English. Given that the newspapers

and magazines used for the corpus analysis are reputable platforms for English usage, the presence of plural forms of uncountable nouns in the corpus indicates a challenge in distinguishing between countable and uncountable nouns and their respective rules in the Pakistani region. If the evidence were from spoken English, there might be some doubt about hasty or mistaken usage. However, newspapers and magazines undergo a rigorous editing process, and consistent instances of plural forms of uncountable nouns suggest that such usage is not an error but a feature of Pakistani English.

Similar results were found in a study conducted in a Japanese context by Kobayashi (2008). The study revealed that errors in plurality were primarily committed by students due to differences in the concept of countable and uncountable nouns between English and Japanese. While this perspective aligns with the current study for words generally uncountable in local languages (e.g., water, income, population), it diverges in instances where local languages treat words like elites (*ameer log*), profits (*faide*), and damages (*choatain*, *nuqsanat*) mainly as countable nouns. Therefore, the current study acknowledges a difference in conceptualization between English and local languages regarding the countability of specific nouns.

Jonsson (2015) reported similar findings for the plurality of uncountable nouns in the context of Swedish-speaking students, partially aligning with the current study's corpus analysis results. In a Sudanese context, Ahmed (2015) identified the lack of knowledge regarding the usage of plural and uncountable nouns among students and teachers as a significant reason behind these deviations. However, in the context of Pakistani English, where writers and editors of the relevant newspapers and magazines are typically highly educated individuals proficient in English, these findings may not be directly applicable. Nevertheless, the dangling or flexible use of plurality can be considered a feature of Pakistani English.

5.4 Use of Yes/No Questions

No data pertaining to this category were found in the available corpora. Several reasons account for these results. The corpus lacked numerous interactive write-ups, and this feature is notably more frequent and apparent in spoken corpora. It can be confidently asserted that in Pakistani Written English, the use of tag questions is not as prevalent as in spoken English. Moreover, even in spoken corpora, the tendency to include inconsistent tag questions is low compared to other varieties of English (Hussain & Mahmood, 2014). Conversely, the inclination to employ invariant tag questions is relatively more frequent in other South Asian Englishes, such as Singaporean English and Indian English (Parviainen, 2016).

A comprehensive literature search conducted by the researchers revealed that only a limited amount of research has been dedicated to studying this syntactic aspect of Pakistani English. There exists a broad spectrum of research areas that demand exploration. The available research is insufficient to fully elucidate the correct pattern of tag questions in Pakistani English.

5.5 Reduplication

The data did not reveal any instances of reduplication in the available corpus. This observation suggests that this linguistic feature might be more prevalent in spoken corpora than in written ones. A comprehensive literature search disclosed that, in the Pakistani context, a substantial amount of research has been dedicated to exploring reduplication in local languages such as Urdu and Punjabi,

but not in Pakistani English. However, one study yielded results in an informal context: the SMS-corpus of Pakistani English demonstrated that individuals used reduplication in their SMS communication, primarily to add emphasis (Hussain, 2013). It is reasonable to assert that formal written Pakistani English does not exhibit reduplication as a prominent feature. No other pertinent research work on reduplication in Pakistani English was found, underscoring the need for further research in this direction.

6. Conclusion

Addressing the research question, certain distinctive features of Pakistani English were evident in some aspects but not in others. Notably, there was a significant inclination towards pluralizing uncountable nouns, influenced primarily by the inter-language effect. Additionally, the positioning of adverbs in sentences exhibited considerable variability, deviating from conventional norms. Moreover, the use of the definite article 'the' lacked consistency and adherence to established rules in numerous instances. However, reduplication and inconsistent use of tag questions, as highlighted by existing models, were not observed in the available corpus, indicating their absence in the scope of this research on Pakistani English.

The primary implication of this study is its contribution to the movement towards local ownership of English in the diaspora. Pakistani English, with its identified features, can now be embraced by ELT practitioners, students, users, and the general public as an authentic variation. The study underscores the potential of corpus-based analyses for multifaceted linguistic investigations, enabling the identification and understanding of linguistic features and variations. Furthermore, this research aligns with a more emancipatory approach to language, moving away from colonial legacies and challenging subjugating ideologies. It also contributes to the counter-hegemonic discourse against the dominance of inner-circle countries.

The findings of this study suggest the need for a nuanced understanding of the distinct identity of English-speaking communities. While existing models for English varieties, especially South Asian Englishes, provide top-down insights, researchers are encouraged to develop models specific to Pakistani English based on available data and findings, fostering a bottom-up approach.

It is crucial to acknowledge the limitations of this study. The focus on a written corpus restricts generalization to written texts only. The corpus, collected from English newspapers and magazines, is representative of these specific genres. Consequently, the findings can be applied primarily to these two forms of written communication. Moreover, the analysis pertains to the writings of experts and field professionals, limiting generalizability to the upper echelons of English writers, academics, and experts, rather than encompassing a broader spectrum of novice or average language users.

Funding: This study was not funded in any shape or form by any party.

Conflict of Interest: The author declares that he has no conflict of interest.

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